

PARADIGMATIC AND SYNTAGMATIC RELATIONS OF LINGUISTIC UNITS IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

Ziyadullayeva Madina Mahmarejab qizi

English teacher at the Department of English translation at Uzbekistan State World Languages
University

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Abstract. *The article discusses several controversial issues considering paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations of linguistic units in Uzbek language. The main focus is given to analyze the differences between paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations and their main types.*

Keywords: *semantic relations, paradigmatic relation, syntagmatic relation, linguistic unit, subordinate, coordinate, predicative.*

Language components are directly connected to one another and work together to create a cohesive system. Regarding this, F. de Saussure (1977) observed that "the development of language units with the weight of their content proceeds in two directions that constitute independent lines. We may understand each of these directions better by contrasting them. They necessitate two brain processes that are essential for language to exist and function". Syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations govern the organization of language. Every linguistic construct has a syntagmatic relationship with other linguistic constructs that are part of the same construction and a paradigmatic relationship with every other linguistic construct that can be replaced for it. The connections of linguistic units resemble axes.

A class's members have intra-systemic relations known as paradigms that are founded on various formal, semantic, and functional concepts. Phonemes, morphemes, lexemes, and sentences are all examples of units with intrinsic paradigmatic relations. A paradigm is a group of related ideas that belong to the same category and are expressed verbally. The concept of paradigm is related to paradigmatic relations. A paradigm has traditionally been thought of as an example of verb and noun conjugation. In modern linguistics, a paradigm is a group of linguistic units that are in opposition to one another while also being connected by some shared characteristic, or, to put it another way, a collection of linguistic units bound together by the relations of similarity and contrast. Scholars distinguish between morphological, syntactic, lexical, word-building or derivational, stylistic, and paradigms of a sentence and a phrase depending on the degree of the class into which language components are structured.

Direct linear relationships between segments of a segmental sequence are known as syntagmatic relations. According to grammatical conventions, words are chained or connected on the syntagmatic axis. Syntagmatic relationships are direct linear connections between segments of a sequence. In other words, syntagmatic interactions are concerned with sentence components. When speech elements follow one another strictly, there exist relationships between them. Two words or word groups combined into one unit—referred to as a syntactic "syntagma"—where one of the words or word groups is modified by the other. A syntagma, which might be a word, a phrase, or an entire sentence, is an intonation-semantic unit that represents one concept in a particular context and setting. Syntagmas generally fall into one of four categories:

1. predicative (a subject and a predicate combined);
2. objective (a verb and its object combined);

3. attributive (a noun combined with its attribute);

4. Adverbial (the conjunction of an adverbial modifier and a modified notional word, such as a verb, adjective, or adverb).

Two semiotic dimensions, paradigm and syntagm, aid in the interrelationship determination of signs. Both concepts are applied as part of the printed analysis to the effective correspondence using signs.

Firstly, Ferdinand Saussure said his opinions about difference between syntagmatic and paradigmatic relations in language. According to Saussure, the linear aspect of language, which prevents two elements from being uttered at the same time, forms the basis of the syntagmatic relationship at the same moment. Syntagmas are made up of these parts when they are arranged sequentially in speech. This idea encompasses not only individual words but also word combinations and complex units of any length, including sentences, compound words, and manufactured words. Only when a sentence contrasts with either what comes before it, what comes after it, or both, is it considered noteworthy. The main distinction between a paradigm and a syntagma is that while syntagmas focus on the situating, paradigms are about substitution. Syntagm and paradigm, which relate to the link with other syntagms, are the source of syntagmatic relations and paradigmatic relations.

According to Seker (2013) quick, direct relationships between units in a segmental sequence are known as syntagmatic relations. A syntagmatic unit is a combination of two words or word clusters, one of which is altered by alternative structures.

Words that co-occur in the same sentence or text are said to have a syntagmatic link, according to Asher (1994). A different kind of semantic relationship between words is a paradigmatic relationship, which allows for the substitution of one term for another within the same categories (Hjorland, 2014). There are different views of linguists about paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations.

Despite the fact that the word dimension has been the subject of numerous studies, Khoo and Na (2006) noted that semantic interactions can also relate to relationships between concepts. There is consensus that paradigmatic relation concerns substitution whereas syntagmatic relation concerns positioning. There are disagreements on whether two concepts or words can have syntagmatic and paradigmatic relationships at the same time. According to Sahlgren (2006), a paradigmatic relation connects concepts that do not appear together in the text. Evens, Litowitz, Markowitz, Smith, and Werner (1980) drew attention to the fact that syntagmatic expression is a viable option for paradigmatic interactions. Jones (2002) discovered that conjunctions and paradigmatic related adjectives frequently co-occur in the same phrases.

A linguistic unit can engage in two different types of relationships. With every unit that may exist in the same environment, it enters into paradigmatic relations. Paradigmatic relations are connections based on similarity concepts. Between the units that can swap out for one another, they exist. For example: in the word-group **chiroyli qiz (beautiful girl)** the word “**chiroyli**” (**beautiful**) is in paradigmatic relations with the words “**hurliqo**” (**attractive**), “**go‘zal**” (**pretty**), “**jozibali**” (**pleasing**) etc.

Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations are divided into several groups according to various principles of similarity. Paradigmatic relations can be of three types:

1. Semantic;
2. Formal;

3. Functional.

Semantic paradigmatic relations are based on meaning of linguistic units. In this relation a word can be replaced by another from the same word class that has the same meaning (synonymy) or with a similar meaning (synonymy), an opposite meaning (antonymy), or a-kind-of meaning (hyponymy). For example: **katta uy, bahaybat uy, keng uy (big house, giant house, large house); semiz qo'y- oriq qo'y (fat sheep-lean sheep).**

Formal paradigmatic relations are based on the form of linguistic elements such as singular/plural form of noun; tenses of verbs. For instance: **ota-otalar (father-fathers) ; yurmoq-yuryapti-yurdi-yurmoqchi (walk-walking-walked- will walk); chiroyli-chiroyliroq-eng chiroyli (beautiful-more beautiful- the most beautiful).**

Functional paradigmatic relations are based on similarity of the function of linguistic units. They are placed between the components that might appear in the same **position. For example: possessive pronouns: mening, uning, sizning, bizning (my, his, your, our)** and others.

Each linguistic unit is a part of a set or sequence of relations based on various formal and functional features, which serves as an expression of these links and dependencies.

These series are created in the field of phonology by comparing phonemes based on vocality or consonantism, voicedness or devoicedness, the nazalization factor, the length factor, etc.

These series are based on numerous subject connections, various word-building dependencies, and correlations of synonymy and antonymy in the vocabulary domain.

Grammatical numbers, cases, persons, tenses, gradations of modalities, sets of sentence-patterns with diverse functional ends, etc. are realized in the field of grammar through series of connected forms.

The term "relations in absentia" (literally, "in the absence") refers to paradigmatic relations, which cannot be explicitly observed in utterances like syntagmatic relations can. As a result, paradigmatic relations are identified with "language," whereas syntagmatic relations are identified with "speech."

Syntagmatic connections must exist in order for any paradigmatic series to be realized because paradigmatic interactions coexist with them in this way.

Likewise, syntagmatic relations of linguistic units are divided into three different groups:

1. Coordinate;
2. Subordinate;
3. Predicative.

Coordinate syntagmatic relations —also known as relations of independence—exist between homogenous linguistic units of equal rank. For instance: **men va sen (I and you); olma bilan anor (apple with granate)** etc.

When one linguistic unit depends on the other, they have a subordinate SR relationship. For example: **o'qit-uvchi (teach-er) -morphological level; aqlli bola (smart boy) -word-group level.**

Primary and secondary predication are interdependent interactions known as predictive syntagmatic relations. For example: **Kamila olmani yoqtiradi. (Kamila likes apple)**

It should be noted that, every linguistic unit are connected to each other and work together in every language. There are different relations between linguistic units which can be paradigmatic and syntagmatic that can also be divided into various types. The main difference between

paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations is that syntagmatic relations can be noticed in speech, however dealing with paradigmatic relations make this impossible. So, paradigmatic relations and syntagmatic relations are classified as "language" and "speech," respectively.

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